

A New Method for the Separation of Lead from Copper and their Subsequent Estimations.

By K. M. SIL, G. C. ROY AND P. N. DAS-GUPTA.

The respective actions of hydrogen peroxide and ammonia on solutions of lead and copper nitrates give rise to a new method of separation of lead from copper. Hydrogen peroxide and ammonia precipitate lead quantitatively from a solution of its nitrate, in the form of a definite compound $Pb_3O_7, 3H_2O$ (Das-Gupta, Roy and Sil, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 657), whereas the reagents have got no action on copper nitrate solution, except the usual formation of a deep blue solution.

It has been found that to separate copper completely, lead requires to be precipitated twice, as in its first precipitate a small amount of copper remains adsorbed. The lead precipitated a second time, in one set of experiments, is taken in a gooch, dried and weighed as $Pb_3O_7, 3H_2O$ and in another set of experiments it is transformed into PbO and weighed as such (Sil, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 137). In the combined filtrates from the first and second precipitations of lead, copper is estimated iodometrically after decomposing hydrogen peroxide left in the filtrate by boiling with nitric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Solutions of lead and copper nitrates were separately made by dissolving about 16.5 g. of lead nitrate and about 24 g. of copper nitrate in 500 c.c. of water respectively and in these solutions lead was estimated as $Pb_3O_7, 3H_2O$ and also as PbO and copper was estimated iodometrically. The precipitation of lead from the lead nitrate solution in presence of nitric acid and the nature of the precipitate, nitric acid is required to dissolve the first lead precipitate. In this study it has been found, that lead can be estimated as $Pb_3O_7, 3H_2O$ in the solution, which contains concentrated nitric acid up to the extent of 0.25 c.c. per 100 c.c. Where the amount of the free acid is greater, the volume of the solution should be so increased by adding water that it may not contain more than 0.25 c.c. of concentrated HNO_3 per 100 c.c.

Separation of Lead from Copper and their Estimations.

Measured volumes of lead and copper nitrate solutions were taken and mixed together, the mixture was diluted to a volume of 100 c.c. with water and one or two drops of dilute nitric acid were added. In this, lead was precipitated by requisite amount of hydrogen peroxide and excess of concentrated ammonia. For every 5 c.c. of the lead nitrate solution, 2 c.c. of 3% hydrogen peroxide and 2 c.c. of concentrated ammonia were added and for every 5 c.c. of the copper nitrate solution in a volume of 100 c.c., 2 c.c. of concentrated ammonia were also added. The precipitate of lead with the blue solution of copper was then heated over a water-bath for 20 minutes; by this time the precipitate attained a crystalline nature. The crystalline lead precipitate was then washed by decantation with hot ammoniacal water (3 or 4 c.c. of conc. NH_4OH in 50 c.c. of water) 3 or 4 times on a filter till the wash-water was colourless. The filtrate was taken in a basin of 500 c.c. capacity, when the amount of copper present was small. In case of the presence of large amounts of copper, the filtrate was taken in a 500 c.c. measuring flask. The filter was then washed into the beaker in which the lead was precipitated, first by a jet of hot water, then pouring on it a few drops of hot dilute nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide and again washing with a jet of hot water. The lead precipitate in the beaker was then dissolved by adding a small quantity of hot dilute nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide and then heating. The solution was then cooled and diluted with water to a volume such that it did not contain more than 0.25 c.c. of free concentrated HNO_3 per 100 c.c. In this solution the precipitation of lead was carried a second time as before and the lead precipitate was filtered through a Jena glass silica-bed crucible, after washing it by decantation with hot ammoniacal water 3 or 4 times, till the filtrate was free from copper and nitrate. The presence of copper was tested first; when copper was found absent, the test for nitrate was also found negative. This filtrate was mixed with the first filtrate and was kept for the estimation of copper. The precipitate on the crucible was finally washed with a little absolute alcohol and dried at $110^\circ\text{-}120^\circ$ for half an hour and weighed as $\text{Pb}_3\text{O}_7, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Either the whole or an aliquot part of the mixed filtrates, according to the amount of copper present, was acidified with nitric acid and evaporated to a volume of not more than 100 c.c. and then boiled for 10 minutes to decompose the hydrogen peroxide present. The

solution was cooled and was made alkaline with excess of ammonia, then acidified with acetic acid and 3 g. of potassium iodide added. The liberated iodine was titrated by *N/10*-sodium thiosulphate solution, which was standardised against *N/10*-copper sulphate solution prepared by dissolving exactly 6.2427 g. of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck's reagent quality) in 500 c.c. of water. From this titration the amount of copper present was calculated.

Several estimations were made, with mixtures of lead and copper nitrate solutions in different proportions, in the way as stated above, the results of which are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.	$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.	H_2O_2 .	Conc. NH_4OH .	$\text{Pb}_5\text{O}_7, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.		Copper	
				Found.	Present.	Found.	Present.
5 c.c.	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.	0.1205 g.	0.1200 g.	0.01310 g.	0.01315 g.
50	1	20	21	1.2060	1.2000	0.01303	„
1	50	2	21	0.0240	0.0240	0.6579	0.6575
5	50	2	22	0.1200	0.1200	0.6579	„
5	10	2	6	0.1203	„	0.1313	0.1315
10	5	4	6	0.2402	0.2400	0.0656	0.06575
5	20	2	10	0.1205	0.1200	0.2629	0.2630
20	5	8	10	0.4810	0.4800	0.0658	0.06575
10	30	4	12	0.2403	0.2400	0.3941	0.3945
30	10	12	16	0.7242	0.7200	0.1313	0.1315
5	5	2	6	0.1203	0.1200	0.0658	0.06575
10	10	4	10	0.2405	0.2400	0.1316	0.1315

Considering the presence of ammonium nitrate in the solution for the precipitation of lead a second time, the second lead precipitate was filtered, dried and transformed to PbO and weighed as such. Several estimations carried in this way are also given in Table II.

TABLE II.

*Pb(NO ₃) ₂ .	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .	H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc. NH ₄ OH.	PbO		Cu	
				Found.	Present.	Found.	Present.
25 c.c.	25 c.c.	10 c.c.	20 c.c.	0.5500 g.	0.5515 g.	0.3286 g.	0.3288 g.
10	40	4	20	0.2200	0.2206	0.5238	0.5260
40	10	16	20	0.8828	0.8824	0.1310	0.1315
2	5	2	4	0.04410	0.04412	0.06579	0.06575
5	2	2	4	0.1107	0.1103	0.0263	0.0263
5	5	2	6	0.1100	0.1103	0.0656	0.06575
10	10	4	10	0.2210	0.2206	0.1313	0.1315

* A different lead nitrate solution.

In conclusion we are much thankful to Principal Dr. D. N. Mallik and Prof. J. C. Das of Carmichael College, Rangpur, for giving us facilities and encouragement to conduct this work in the Chemical Laboratory of the College.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
CARMICHAEL COLLEGE, RANGPUR.

Received December 7, 1936.